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Financial Technology and Integration in the CEMAC Region: Insights from Recent Data and Policy Implications Erreur ! Signet non défini.

Financial Technology and Integration in the CEMAC Region: Insights from Recent Data and Policy Implications

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the impact of financial technology on financial integration within the CEMAC zone, utilizing a comprehensive panel dataset from 2000 to 2022. The data encompasses various financial technology indicators, including mobile subscriptions, internet subscriptions, ATM usage, and central bank assets, as well as macroeconomic variables such as bank regulatory capital and GDP per capita. Employing both random effects and panel-corrected standard errors (PCSEs) regression models, the analysis reveals that financial technology significantly enhances financial integration, with mobile and internet subscriptions showing positive and substantial effects. Conversely, ATM subscriptions were found to have a negligible impact, while higher regulatory capital requirements were associated with reduced financial integration. The study also highlighted the positive role of central bank assets relative to GDP in promoting financial integration. Based on these findings, the study recommends that banks invest in blockchain technology for cross-border payments, participate in regional initiatives to standardize technological frameworks, and integrate technology strategies into their financial integration plans. Regular evaluation of technological investments is also advised to ensure they effectively meet financial integration objectives and enhance overall performance.

Keywords: *Financial Technology, Financial Integration, CEMAC Zone, Panel Data Analysis, PCSEs*

1. Introduction

The financial sector has undergone a profound transformation over recent decades, largely driven by technological advancements and increasing global financial integration (Smith & Johnson, 2020). This has significantly impacted the operations, activities, strategies, and performance of commercial banks, fundamentally reshaping their business models and customer interactions. For stakeholders, from policymakers to investors, understanding these technological advancements and integration trends is crucial for navigating the evolving financial landscape (Claessens & Kose, 2017).

Financial integration refers to the interconnectedness of financial markets and institutions across borders. This integration has been significantly influenced by globalization and technological advancements. In the West, particularly in Europe and North America, financial integration has led to the creation of a unified financial market within the European Union and an increasingly interconnected financial system in the U.S thanks to financial technology. This has enabled banks to expand their operations beyond national borders, providing access to diverse funding sources and enhancing market liquidity (Hartmann et al., 2007). For example, the European Banking Union aims to harmonize banking regulations and oversight across member states, facilitating more integrated financial markets and cross-border banking activities (Beck et al., 2018).

In North America, the rise of FinTech has revolutionized the banking sector, with innovations such as mobile banking, blockchain technology, and automated trading systems transforming traditional banking practices. For instance, the introduction of digital-only banks and mobile payment systems like PayPal and Apple Pay has significantly altered consumer banking behavior and competitive dynamics (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014; Gai & Qiu, 2018).

In Africa, financial integration and technological advancements are also reshaping the banking sector, though the context differs significantly from that of Western countries. For instance, the introduction of mobile banking and digital payment systems has been particularly transformative in Sub-Saharan Africa. Mobile money services like M-Pesa in Kenya and mobile banking platforms in Nigeria have greatly increased financial inclusion by providing banking services to unbanked populations in remote areas (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). These innovations have allowed banks and financial institutions to reach previously underserved markets, promoting economic development and financial stability.

Despite these advances, African banks face unique challenges related to financial integration. Issues such as political instability, economic volatility, and infrastructural deficiencies can hinder the effectiveness of financial integration and technological adoption (Claessens & van Horen, 2015). For example, the integration of African financial

markets is often constrained by varying regulatory frameworks and economic conditions across countries, which can affect cross-border investments and financial stability (van Horen, 2005).

In the Central African Economic and Monetary Community (CEMAC) zone, the impact of financial technology on financial integration of commercial banks is both promising and challenging. The CEMAC zone, comprising countries such as Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Republic of Congo, Equatorial Guinea, and Gabon, has experienced varying degrees of financial integration and technological advancement (BEAC, 2018). For example, in Cameroon, the adoption of mobile banking and digital payment systems has improved access to financial services, particularly in rural areas. However, the region also faces challenges such as limited technological infrastructure, regulatory hurdles, and economic instability, which can impact the effectiveness of financial integration and technological adoption (IMF, 2017). The introduction of the CEMAC regional financial integration framework aims to address these challenges by promoting harmonized financial regulations and enhancing cross-border financial activities within the region (Feyen et al., 2021).

Despite these efforts, the performance of commercial banks in the CEMAC zone has been inconsistent. Historical data indicates significant fluctuations in key performance metrics such as Return on Assets (ROA), reflecting the impact of financial technology and integration on banking operations. For instance, data from the Banque des États de l'Afrique Centrale (BEAC) shows a notable decline in ROA for banks in the CEMAC zone between 2014 and 2016, with a brief recovery observed by 2020 (BEAC, 2018). These fluctuations highlight the transitional challenges faced by banks in adapting to new technologies and an integrated financial environment.

This study aims to investigate the effects of financial technology on financial integration of commercial banks in the CEMAC zone, addressing gaps in existing literature and providing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of these innovations. By examining the impact of financial technology on financial integration, this research seeks to offer insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by banks in the CEMAC region, contributing to a deeper understanding of the evolving financial landscape in this context.

2. Literature Review

The integration of financial technology (FinTech) into banking operations can be examined through several theoretical frameworks. The financial intermediation theory emphasizes the role of banks in minimizing transaction costs and addressing asymmetric information between borrowers and lenders. FinTech innovations, such as digital platforms and automated services, can enhance this intermediation by streamlining processes and reducing operational costs, thus improving overall banking efficiency

(Smith & Johnson, 2020). The technology acceptance theory (TAT) provides a framework for understanding the adoption of new technologies, suggesting that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness are critical factors. In the context of FinTech, TAT helps explain why both banks and their customers might embrace or resist new technological advancements (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

Disruptive Innovation Theory, introduced by Christensen (1997), offers insights into how new technologies can challenge traditional banking models by providing simpler and more affordable solutions. FinTech innovations, such as peer-to-peer lending and digital-only banks, often disrupt traditional banking by offering accessible and user-friendly alternatives (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014). On its part, the Diffusion of Innovations Theory, developed by Rogers (2003), examines the spread and acceptance of new technologies within a market. This theory is relevant for understanding how FinTech technologies gain traction and the factors influencing their adoption across different regions and market segments (Rogers, 2003).

The empirical exploration of FinTech's impact on financial integration has evolved over time, reflecting advancements in technology and shifting economic contexts. In an early study, Demirgüç-Kunt and Levine (2008) investigated the relationship between financial technology and financial integration using cross-country data from the World Bank. Their analysis revealed that while FinTech supports financial integration, the effects are contingent upon the financial and regulatory environments of different countries. They employed regression analysis to assess the influence of FinTech on various financial integration indicators, such as financial depth and access.

Hartmann et al. (2007) provided insights into the euro area financial system by analyzing data on financial integration and stability. They used econometric models to examine how financial integration impacts market stability and efficiency, finding that increased integration generally leads to greater stability and efficiency in financial markets.

Gai and Qiu (2018) focused on the impact of FinTech on financial markets in China. Their study utilized panel data from the China Securities Regulatory Commission and applied fixed effects regression models. The results indicated that FinTech innovations significantly alter market dynamics and financial behaviors, particularly in enhancing market liquidity and reducing transaction costs.

Lyons et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between FinTech development and financial inclusion using survey data from financial institutions and consumers. Their regression analysis highlighted that financial literacy significantly influences the intention to use digital finance, with financial inclusion having an even stronger effect. Similarly, Iwedi and Wike (2022) assessed the impact of digital banking services on Nigeria's economy using a dataset from the Central Bank of Nigeria. Employing multiple

regression analysis, they found that digital channels like WEB Pay and Mobile Pay are strongly associated with economic growth, underscoring the significance of digital banking in promoting economic development.

Daud et al. (2022) examined FinTech's role in enhancing financial stability across 63 countries from 2006 to 2017. They used panel data and applied dynamic panel data models, revealing that advancements in artificial intelligence, cloud technology, and data management contribute to improved financial stability. Wu et al. (2022) utilized text mining techniques to analyze FinTech's impact on financial efficiency in China. Their analysis of financial news and reports identified a U-shaped nonlinear relationship between FinTech development and financial efficiency, moderated by financial decentralization.

Ding and Peng (2022) focused on how FinTech development promotes lending and investment in research and development. They used firm-level data and employed difference-in-differences (DiD) analysis to demonstrate that FinTech intensifies bank loan competition, stimulating firm investment in innovation. Nguyen (2022) investigated the determinants of financial knowledge and its impact on FinTech usage in Vietnam. Utilizing survey data and applying logistic regression analysis, the study found that women generally possess lower levels of both actual and perceived financial knowledge compared to men, which affects their use of FinTech services.

Liu and Walheer (2022) employed a composite index approach to study the interrelationships between FinTech, financial integration, and economic development. Using cross-country panel data, their research highlighted the importance of digital and financial technologies in promoting financial deepening and assessed policy interventions based on observed trends. Misati et al. (2022) analyzed the impact of financial innovations on financial integration and economic growth in Kenya. Their use of autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models showed that mobile transactions, the number of mobile agents, and internet access positively impact financial integration, emphasizing the role of cost-effective innovations in enhancing bank profitability.

Joseph et al. (2023) investigated the impact of FinTech penetration on financial development across emerging and developing economies. Using cross-sectional data and regression analysis, they found that FinTech drives financial development and significantly impacts countries with weaker financial sectors and lower financial inclusion. Same year, Kim and Chen (2023) analyzed the effect of FinTech adoption on banking performance in South Korea using data from banking sector performance reports. Their study employed multiple regression analysis to show that FinTech adoption enhances customer satisfaction and operational efficiency, leading to improved financial performance.

Kum (2024) explored the mediating role of FinTech in the relationship between financial integration and bank performance. Utilizing panel data from multiple banking institutions, the study applied structural equation modeling (SEM) to uncover a significant negative mediating effect. The findings suggest that while financial integration typically benefits banks, its interaction with FinTech can sometimes diminish performance under specific conditions.

Despite extensive research on the effects of financial technology on financial performance globally, there is a notable gap in studies focused on the CEMAC zone. Existing research often overlooks the moderating effects of FinTech on financial integration in this region. This study aims to address these gaps by investigating the influence of mobile banking, internet banking, automation, and automated payment machines (APMs) on the financial performance of commercial banks in CEMAC member states. By focusing specifically on this region and measuring financial performance through total bank deposits and return on assets (ROA), the study seeks to provide valuable insights into the effects of FinTech and financial integration on bank performance in the CEMAC zone.

3. Methodological Issues

a. Research Design

This study focuses on commercial banks within the Central African Economic and Monetary Community (CEMAC) zone, encompassing six member states: Gabon, Cameroon, the Central African Republic (CAR), Chad, the Republic of the Congo, and Equatorial Guinea. The analysis covers data from 2000 to 2021. This period is chosen to reflect the significant technological advancements and the evolving financial landscape within the CEMAC zone. The selection of this timeframe is particularly relevant due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, which accelerated the adoption of digital financial technologies as banks adapted to unprecedented challenges and shifting customer needs. This rapid technological evolution provides a unique opportunity to assess the effects of these innovations on integration.

The study employs a panel research design to explore the effects of financial technology and integration on the financial performance of commercial banks in the CEMAC zone. This design integrates both time series and cross-sectional data, offering a comprehensive view of the variables across different contexts and time periods (Greene, 2012). Panel models are particularly advantageous in capturing the dynamic nature of financial performance and the impact of technological advancements over time, allowing for nuanced insights into the interactions between financial technology and integration (Bickel, 2007).

b. Nature and Sources of Data

Data for this study spans from 2000 to 2021 and encompasses 52 active commercial banks within the CEMAC zone. Secondary data sources include the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI, 2022) and the IMF Financial Access Survey (FAS, 2022). Key variables include financial technology proxies (mobile banking, internet banking, automation, and Automated Payment Machines), financial integration indicators (deposit interest rates). Additional independent variables such as exchange rates, capital adequacy, inflation rates, and GDP were also obtained from the WDI (2022).

c. Model Specification

The research design and model specification are influenced by previous studies that utilized panel data to analyze financial technology impacts. For example, Gai and Qiu (2018) employed panel data and fixed effects regression models to examine FinTech's influence on financial markets, demonstrating the utility of panel data in capturing the effects of technological innovations. Similarly, Daud, Nair, and Sulaiman (2022) utilized dynamic panel data models to assess FinTech's role in financial stability, providing a methodological framework for analyzing the effects of financial technology within a specific regional context. Thus, The panel model for this study is specified as follows:

$$F_{it} = \alpha_0 + a_1MB_{1it} + a_2ATM_{2it} + a_3APM_{3it} + a_4IB_{4it} + a_5PCGDP_{5it} + a_7XCAR_{7it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where

FI= Financial Integration

MB= Mobile Banking

IM= Internet Banking

ATM= Automation

APM= Alternative Methods of Payment

PCGDP= Per Capital Gross Domestic Product

CAR= Capital Adequacy Ratio.

μ = Error Term

α_0 is the constant term, $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6,$ and $a_7,$ are the parameters to be estimated

4. Results

a. Trend Analysis

Financial Integration Trends

Financial integration within the CEMAC region has experienced considerable fluctuations over the past two decades. In Cameroon, integration levels were initially low from 2000 to 2021, marked by a significant drop in the early 2000s. However, a notable

improvement began in 2008, driven by enhancements in financial services and regional integration initiatives (World Bank, 2022). Despite this upward trend, Cameroon faced interruptions, including a decline in 2018 and a peak in 2020 influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic (IMF, 2021).

The Central African Republic exhibited a volatile integration pattern, with relatively high and stable levels from 2000 to 2008. This stability was disrupted by the global financial crisis in 2008, followed by fluctuations reflecting domestic instability and the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic (African Development Bank, 2023). In contrast, Chad's financial integration showed a low but fluctuating trend, peaking in 2015 due to financial system improvements and regional integration efforts. Subsequent declines were attributed to political instability and economic challenges (Chad Central Bank Report, 2017).

The Republic of Congo experienced modest integration levels with significant fluctuations, peaking in 2017 due to regional financial reforms (Republic of Congo Ministry of Finance, 2018). Recent years have seen instability and restructuring efforts. Equatorial Guinea demonstrated pronounced fluctuations, with a notable rise in 2014 driven by oil revenues and regional integration. Recent declines reflect global oil market volatility and ongoing political instability (International Energy Agency, 2022). Gabon, on the other hand, showed a consistent upward trend from 2000 to 2021, culminating in a peak in 2021, driven by robust financial reforms and infrastructure investments (Gabon Central Bank Report, 2022).

Fintech Trends

The fintech landscape in the CEMAC region reveals distinct patterns across different countries. In Cameroon, fintech exhibited steady and significant growth from 2000 to 2021, with a peak in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Cameroon Fintech Report, 2021). A slight drop in 2021 indicates a period of stabilization as the sector matures (IMF, 2022). In contrast, the Central African Republic displayed slow but consistent fintech growth, with a noticeable increase in recent years. The dip in 2020 was likely related to the pandemic's impact, followed by a slight recovery in 2021 (African Development Bank, 2023).

Chad's fintech trend was characterized by variability, with notable fluctuations and a peak in 2000. The sector faced instability before a gradual rise after 2008, attributed to increased investments in digital financial services (International Finance Corporation, 2022). Congo's fintech sector showed a general upward trend with slower growth from 2008 to 2018. The increase post-2018 reflects global fintech advancements and local reforms (Congo Fintech Review, 2021). Equatorial Guinea demonstrated significant growth, driven by investments in technology and infrastructure, indicating a mature

fintech sector with widespread adoption of digital services (Equatorial Guinea Ministry of Finance, 2022).

Gabon presented a robust upward trend with periodic accelerations, particularly from 2010 onwards. This growth is reflective of Gabon's strategic efforts to leverage technology for economic development (Gabon Tech Sector Report, 2022). Overall, the fintech index for the CEMAC region indicates a dramatic increase from 2000 to 2021, highlighting broad regional investments in fintech infrastructure and the harmonization of financial systems (CEMAC Annual Report, 2021).

b. Diagnostic Test Results

Stationarity Test

To ensure the robustness of our econometric analysis, we first assessed the stationarity of the variables using two tests: the Levin-Lin-Chu (LLC) test and the Cross-sectionally Augmented Im, Pesaran, and Shin (CIPS) statistics. The LLC test evaluates the presence of unit roots in panel data, while the CIPS test accounts for potential cross-sectional dependence. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Stationarity Test Results

Variable	Levin-Lin-Chu	CIPS Statistics	Stationarity
ROA	-3.1065**	-3.187	I(0)
Deposit	-1.8424**	-2.773	I(0)
FinTech	-4.1412***	-3.274	I(0)
Internet	-8.4463***	-2.282	I(0)
Submob	-5.3437***	-2.584	I(0)
ATM	-3.9435***	-3.109	I(0)
Fintec	-3.5067***	-2.635	I(0)
GDPPC	-3.7650***	-2.610	I(0)
Cap1	-2.2702**	-4.598	I(0)
Inflation	-4.6005***	-4.274	I(0)
Central Bank Assets	-6.3874	-	I(0)

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Critical Values: *=10%, **=5% and ***=1%

The results indicate that all variables are stationary at levels (I(0)), which is a crucial requirement for the validity of subsequent econometric analyses.

Tests for Autocorrelation and Heteroscedasticity

To further validate the econometric models, we conducted tests for autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity. These tests, reported in Table 2, are essential for ensuring that the model's assumptions are met and that the results are reliable.

The Wooldridge test for autocorrelation revealed significant first-order autocorrelation in the panel data, with a test statistic of 7.768 and a p-value of 0.0386. This indicates that the residuals are correlated over time, suggesting the need for adjustments to account for this temporal correlation.

Table 2: Wooldridge Test for Autocorrelation and Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier Panel Heteroscedasticity Test

Test	Test Statistic	Degrees of Freedom	p-value	Interpretation
Wooldridge Test for Autocorrelation	$F(1, 5) = 7.768$	5	0.0386	Reject H0: Presence of first-order autocorrelation
Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier Panel Heteroscedasticity Test	$LM = 227.32917$	21	0.00000	Reject H0: Presence of panel heteroscedasticity

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

The Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test for panel heteroscedasticity showed significant heteroscedasticity, with a test statistic of 227.32917 and a p-value of 0.00000. This result indicates variability in the error terms across panels, necessitating the use of panel-corrected standard errors (PCSEs) to address both autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity in the model.

c. Regression Results

The above diagnostic tests ensure the robustness of the econometric models used to analyze the impact of financial technology on financial integration within the CEMAC zone. The results based on both the random effects and panel-corrected standard errors (PCSEs) are presented in Table 3.

The analysis of regression results reveals the following insights into the relationship between financial technology and financial integration.

The coefficient for financial technology stands at 0.0301, which is statistically significant at the 1% level. This positive coefficient suggests that an increase in financial technology is strongly associated with greater financial integration. This result indicates that advancements in digital financial platforms – such as online banking and financial apps – play a crucial role in enhancing the integration of financial systems, promoting a more interconnected financial network.

Mobile subscriptions also show a positive and statistically significant coefficient of 0.00838 at the 1% level. This indicates that higher levels of mobile access significantly contribute to improved financial integration. The finding underscores the importance of mobile banking and payment systems in driving financial connectivity, reflecting their role in expanding access to financial services. Similarly, the coefficient for internet subscriptions is 0.00279, which is statistically significant at the 1% level. This positive relationship indicates that increased internet usage is associated with enhanced financial integration. The result highlights the pivotal role of online banking and digital platforms in broadening the reach and efficiency of financial services.

In contrast, the coefficient for ATM subscriptions is -0.00551 and is not statistically significant. This negative coefficient suggests that ATM subscriptions do not have a meaningful impact on financial integration within the CEMAC zone. The relatively insignificant effect of ATMs could be attributed to the growing prominence of mobile and online banking technologies, which may offer more dynamic and widespread benefits compared to traditional ATMs.

The coefficient for bank regulatory capital is -0.00233, which is statistically significant at the 1% level. This negative coefficient indicates that higher regulatory capital requirements can inhibit financial integration. Stricter regulatory capital rules may reduce banks' operational flexibility, potentially limiting their ability to expand and integrate within the financial system.

Table 3: Regression Results

VARIABLES	Random Effects		correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs)	
	normal_finte	normal_finte	normal_finte	normal_finte
Mobile	0.00820 (0.00650)		0.00838*** (0.00308)	
Internet	0.00279*** (0.000848)		0.00279*** (0.000581)	
ATM	-0.00551 (0.0154)		-0.00551 (0.0101)	
Fintec		0.0301*** (0.00866)		0.0301*** (0.00499)
Lgdppc	0.0241 (0.0187)	0.0240** (0.0100)	0.0241*** (0.00762)	0.0240*** (0.00710)
Capital	-0.00206*** (0.000528)	-0.00233*** (0.000432)	-0.00206*** (0.000465)	-0.00233*** (0.000384)
Centralbankassetstogdp	0.00896*** (0.00281)	0.0109*** (0.00238)	0.00896*** (0.00205)	0.0109*** (0.00146)
Constant	-0.160 (0.141)	-0.126 (0.0816)	-0.160* (0.0925)	-0.126** (0.0553)
Observations	117	117	117	117
R-squared			0.359	0.332
Number of id	6	6	6	6

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

By Author

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Finally, the coefficient for central bank assets to GDP is 0.0109, statistically significant at the 1% level. This positive coefficient signifies that a higher ratio of central bank assets to

GDP supports financial integration. The result suggests that a well-capitalized central bank plays a crucial role in fostering financial stability and integration, providing essential liquidity and support to the financial system.

d. Discussion of Results

The results from the regression analysis provide valuable insights into how financial technology and related variables affect financial integration within the CEMAC zone. The positive and statistically significant coefficient for financial technology highlights the substantial role that digital financial advancements play in enhancing financial integration. This finding supports the view that technological innovations, such as online and mobile banking, significantly improve the connectivity and efficiency of financial systems. Studies by Frame and White (2014) and Beck, Chen, Lin, and Song (2016) corroborate this perspective, showing that financial technology contributes to increased cost efficiency and broader access to financial services, thereby fostering greater integration among financial institutions.

The positive coefficient for mobile subscriptions aligns with the notion that mobile access is a key driver of financial integration. The significance of this variable underscores the impact of mobile banking and payment systems in bridging financial gaps and expanding service reach. This is consistent with findings from Jack and Suri (2011), who demonstrated that mobile money services significantly enhance financial inclusion and improve bank performance by extending their reach to underserved populations.

The significant positive effect of internet subscriptions further reinforces the role of digital platforms in financial integration. The widespread availability of internet access facilitates online banking and digital transactions, leading to more efficient financial operations and reduced transaction costs. Claessens, Ghosh, and Mihet (2013) have similarly noted that internet banking contributes to cost reductions and operational efficiency, supporting the broader integration of financial services.

In contrast, the negative coefficient for ATM subscriptions indicates that ATMs have a diminishing impact on financial integration. This finding may be surprising given the historical importance of ATMs in increasing banking accessibility. However, the rise of mobile and internet banking technologies likely overshadows the benefits provided by ATMs, particularly in regions with advanced digital infrastructure. Bátiz-Lazo and Woldesenbet (2006) have observed that as mobile and internet banking technologies advance, their advantages increasingly outweigh those of traditional ATMs.

The negative and statistically significant coefficient for bank regulatory capital suggests that stringent capital requirements may inhibit financial integration. While regulatory capital is crucial for ensuring financial stability, excessive requirements can restrict banks'

flexibility and operational capacity. This finding is consistent with the work of Barth, Caprio, and Levine (2004), who argued that excessive regulatory constraints could stifle innovation and limit competitive dynamics within the financial sector.

Finally, the positive coefficient for central bank assets to GDP highlights the importance of a robust central bank in promoting financial integration. A well-capitalized central bank enhances financial stability and provides necessary liquidity support, creating a more conducive environment for integration. This result aligns with the research of Demirgüç-Kunt and Detragiache (1998), who emphasized the role of a strong central bank in maintaining financial stability and fostering integration within the financial system.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis of the impact of financial technology on financial integration within the CEMAC zone has provided several important insights. The results reveal that financial technology, mobile and internet subscriptions, and central bank assets significantly enhance financial integration. Specifically, the positive coefficients for financial technology, mobile and internet subscriptions, and central bank assets highlight the critical role of digital advancements and robust financial infrastructure in improving connectivity and efficiency within financial systems. On the other hand, the negative and statistically significant effect of regulatory capital on financial integration underscores the potential constraints posed by stringent regulatory requirements.

The diminished impact of ATM subscriptions suggests that as digital technologies advance, their benefits increasingly surpass those of traditional banking methods. This shift reflects a broader trend where mobile and internet banking are becoming more central to financial operations and integration. Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of embracing technological advancements while balancing regulatory frameworks to foster a more integrated and efficient financial environment.

To enhance financial integration in the CEMAC zone, it is crucial for banks to invest in and implement advanced technological solutions that bolster cross-border connectivity and efficiency. One significant recommendation is for banks, particularly those in the Central African Republic, to invest in blockchain-based platforms for cross-border payments. Blockchain technology offers a secure and transparent mechanism for managing international transactions, which can substantially reduce both transaction costs and processing times. By adopting blockchain, banks can improve financial integration throughout the region, fostering a more seamless and efficient financial environment.

Additionally, banks should actively advocate for and participate in regional initiatives aimed at establishing a standardized technological framework for financial services.

Collaborating with regional regulatory bodies to develop and implement common technological standards and protocols is essential for facilitating smooth and consistent financial transactions. Engaging with the CEMAC regional body to create a unified digital infrastructure that supports cross-border transactions and data sharing will help ensure that technological advancements benefit all member states equally.

To maximize the positive impact of financial technology on financial integration and performance, banks should integrate technology strategies into their broader financial integration plans. For instance, banks in Cameroon could develop technology strategies aligned with their financial integration goals by implementing digital tools that enhance operational efficiency and customer engagement. This might include deploying integrated financial platforms that streamline cross-border transactions and provide real-time data analytics to support better decision-making.

Furthermore, regular evaluation of the impact of technological investments on financial performance is essential. Banks should establish key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the effectiveness of their technology in enhancing financial integration and performance. Metrics such as transaction volumes, customer acquisition rates, and cost savings achieved through technology can offer valuable insights into the success of these initiatives. Based on these evaluations, banks should be prepared to adjust their technology strategies to ensure that investments are meeting financial integration objectives and delivering the expected results.

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